

Hot asphaltting on orthotropic bridge decks – investigation on fatigue loading

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ABSTRACT

While there is clear evidence, that the increasing loads from the increasing traffic volume – in particular heavy vehicles – are causing a quite dramatic rise of number of bridges that have to deal with fatigue issues, it has been observed also that the renewal of the asphalt deck seems to cause fatigue problems. On road-bridges, hot asphalt is installed to provide a level and waterproof surface. That wearing surface however needs occasional renewal. On a number of steel highway bridges, it has been observed that after such asphalt exchange fatigue cracks at the welds of the orthotropic bridge decks have occurred increasingly. The German Federal Highway Research Institute BASt has assigned a research project to RWTH Aachen University Institute of Steel Construction to evaluate the response of steel-bridges to those time- and location-dependent, nonlinear temperature profiles. On two exemplary steel bridges – one with a hollow box main girder and one with two open main girders – data has been collected during the process of hot asphaltting: temperature profiles across the cross section as well as some strain measurements at selected hot spots. With a detailed and advanced model using commercial FEM software it has been possible to simulate precisely the transient thermal profile across the cross section. However, when it comes to derive from that the stress loading for the global structure of such long, large-span bridges, those FEM software comes to their limit. Therefore, a simplified software-based lamella-model has been developed, with the partition of the bridge into rectangular beam-lamellas. This enables to consider the nonlinear temperature and to calculate the inner-forces and displacements along the bridge, which then in return can be combined with the stresses derived from the local FEM model. The results from that calculations could be validated with the measurement data and thus could confirm the stresses during hot asphaltting.

Keywords: steel bridges, orthotropic deck, hot asphaltting, fatigue

1 INTRODUCTION

Installation of the asphalt pavement and associated stress and temperature impacts onto the structure are not being considered so far during the structural design of bridges, although in particular for steel orthotropic decks an increase of weld cracks has been observed during the bridge inspections following such renewal of the asphalt. It seems obvious that such damages are resulting from the loading conditions that are acting onto the structure during the works for the asphalt. It could be, for example, that this is in particular from the dynamic vibrations during the cut out of the top layer of the asphalt or it may be a result from the thermal loading due to the laying of the hot asphalt. Surely the operation of larger and more powerful asphalt pavers is aggravating that challenge. Within earlier research projects from the German Federal Highway Research Institute BASt (Bundesanstalt für Straßenwesen) that complex issue has been already addressed and some fundamentals have been derived. In particular with regard to the temperature impact some comprehensive measurement campaigns have been set up and carried out on a number of bridges. (1), (2)

It is also noticeable that the process for some normative regulations has been started: At least now some general reference is being introduced into the recent proposal of prEN 1991-1-5: 2023 (3) to consider hot asphalt.

Therefore, the scope of this research project has been to develop an approach to determine the impact of hot asphalt on the bridge structure of long steel bridges and to validate it with measurement data. During the process of hot asphalt laying transient temperature fields progress longitudinal and across the bridge deck, causing temperature induced mechanical stresses as well as bridge deformations that lead to loads in particular at the abutments.

For two representative steel bridges in Germany, the “Hochmoselbrücke” with a box section and the “Mühlenfließbrücke” with an open cross section, the transient temperature fields have been investigated within this project. At both bridges, in the past, the process of laying mastic asphalt of the protective layer has been monitored over time at selected points of the cross section and that data has been available. Fig. 1 illustrates for example from the Hochmoselbrücke: It is shown where the temperature sensors have been installed and the measured temperature curves over time are plotted. At the deck plate temperatures of approximately 90°C occur within about 20 minutes. Also, that data shows that there is a significant temperature gradient over the cross section during that first hour after the asphalt.

Fig. 1. Temperature measurements over the cross girder at the German Hochmoselbrücke – photograph of the installed sensors (above left) and position of sensors (above right), temperature over time plot of the sensors after hot asphalt laying the bridge deck (below)

2 FE-MODELLING FOR SIMULATION OF TEMPERATURE FIELDS

For both bridges detailed FEM section-models have been created using the software tool ANSYS (4) (Fig. 2, upper row). These models allow a thermal transient simulation of the hot asphaltting, so that the temperature development within the structure of the orthotropic deck, i.e. deck plate, longitudinal stiffeners, cross girder (and in particular also at the inter-section of longitudinal stiffener and cross girder) can be determined. Fig. 2, bottom row, shows exemplarily the temperature distribution across the section after hot asphaltting.

Fig. 2. FEM section-models for the Hochmoselbrücke (left) and for the Mühlenfließbrücke (right) with temperature distribution after hot asphaltting (below)

With the measurement data during the hot asphaltting of the bridges, taken in-field, the models can be calibrated: A very good agreement has been achieved, since the model incorporates precise section geometries as well as physical characteristics with regard to temperature analysis, so that possible errors or ambiguities can be clarified. Fig. 3 compares exemplarily the simulated temperature curves at the deck plate as well as for the bottom side of the longitudinal rib with the corresponding measurement plot at the Hochmoselbrücke.

Fig. 3. Calibration of transient temperature evolution for the Hochmoselbrücke – comparison of measurement data and FE results at two exemplary points

With that calibrated and verified model, it has been possible to carry out an extensive parametric study to investigate both process dependent as well as meteorological climate dependent boundary conditions.

In the following Table 1 all investigated parameters are given, with a range for each. That parametric range (min- and max-values) to be used as loading conditions for the FEM calculations on the section model, has been quantified based on literature and market analysis of pavers for laying mastic asphalt.

This ensures a realistic range of parameters, while the basic functions of the asphalt layer are met (i.e. processability, stability, surface structure/ grip, durability) for all investigated parameters.

Table 1. Variation of parametric study on both selected steel bridges

Parameter	Variation							
Number of paving tracks (total width of asphalt: 2 driving lanes + emergency lane)	1		2			4		
Asphalt laying temperature	180 °C		200 °C			230 °C		
Initial temperature, const. over CS temperature deck plate temperature other steel	5 °C 5 °C	10 °C 10 °C	17 °C 17 °C	25 °C 25 °C	30 °C 30 °C			
Initial temperature, gradient over CS temperature deck plate temperature other steel	5 °C 0 °C	15 °C 5 °C	17 °C 17 °C	25 °C 10 °C	35 °C 10 °C	35 °C 17 °C	50 °C 25 °C	
Radiation Asphalt emission ratio ϵ	0.00		0.50			0.93		
Laying speed [m/min]	0.5		1.0		1.5		2.5	
Protective layer thickness [cm]	2.5		3.0		3.5		5.0	
Top layer thickness [cm]	3.5		4.0			4.5		
Type of construction and waterproofing system thickness [mm]	Type of construction 2				Type of construction 1			
	5.0	7.5	10.0	12.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5
Deck plate thickness [mm]	10		12			14		

3 COMBINED STRESS ANALYSIS USING FEM AND A LAMELLA MODEL

Based on the temperature fields derived from the thermal transient simulations the transient, temperature induced mechanical stresses over the section of the orthotropic plate as well as bridge deformations are to be determined. Those stresses are on the one hand those locally induced by the temperature field, but at the same time also from the global structural behaviour effected by the global temperature development. For one of the examined bridges, the “Mühlenfließbrücke”, also measurement data for these stresses during hot asphaltting has been on hand (5).

Simulating those stresses therefore means that it is necessary to model the whole bridge structure to derive global stresses over the bridge length while at the same time it is necessary to maintain a sufficient, i.e. detailed, mesh resolution to derive the detailed local stresses. It turned out to be impossible to achieve both criteria for those investigated large span steel bridges with one single FEM model, even with today's highly developed university IT-clusters and different approaches for adjusting the meshing. Therefore, some path for a model reduction needed to be developed in terms of a new calculation approach with combining a local FEM section model with a separate lamella-model covering the other global effects. Fig. 4 shows the two separate section models, where due to its simplicity the section model of the lamella model may be extended over the whole length of the bridge, in this case of the Mühlenfließbrücke over some 750 metres.

Fig. 4. Combination of FEM section model and corresponding lamella model for the Mühlenfließbrücke

The lamella model is actually set up of three separate lamella models for the investigated bridge “Mühlenfließbrücke”, one for the bridge deck and one each for the two main girders adjacent to the deck. The lamella models with matrices for stiffness, loading and boundary conditions are being written using the mathematical computer tool MATLAB (6). Both lamella models are being coupled under equilibrium conditions and considering shear strain effects (as indicated in Fig. 5 by the large plus sign). The thermal transient fields determined with the local FEM-model are to be taken as input data.

Fig. 5. Set up of lamella model for deck plate and two main girders for the Mühlenfließbrücke

To verify that approach, the calculated stresses using that combined stress analysis has been compared with a full FEM analysis for a hypothetical two-span bridge model of the “Mühlenfließbrücke” and match very well. Furthermore, the combined stress analysis could also be validated for the whole length “Mühlenfließbrücke” when evaluating the measurement data in comparison with the calculated stresses, as can be seen in Fig. 6. In particular the stress development at the top of the main girder is simulated very precisely. Also, by superposing the stresses from the global lamella model with those from the local FEM simulation, it is possible to determine the hot-spot stresses of the orthotropic bridge deck.

Fig. 6. Stress development over time at the top of the main girder for the Mühlenfließbrücke – comparison of measurement data and lamella model results

For the most important parameters – with regard to expected effects on the global stresses – of the previous parametric study on the thermal simulations (cf. Table 1 above) additional calculations have been carried out with the combined stress analysis using the lamella model to determine the decisive longitudinal stresses over the cross section as well as the deformations of the bridge at the first and end abutment:

- Width of asphalt pavement / number of paving tracks
- Asphaltting process
 - o Asphalt laying temperature
 - o Laying speed
- Meteorological climate dependent boundary conditions
 - o Initial temperature, constant over CS
 - o Initial temperature, gradient over CS

4 RESULTS

4.1 Temperature fields simulated with FEM section-models

When looking at those asphaltting process dependent parameters the most significant effects can be seen by a variation of the initial asphalt laying temperature, the thickness of the protective layer and the choice of the type of construction with the waterproofing system thickness. On the other hand, the effects from a variation of the laying speed and of the top layer thickness are less significant. As an example, the upper graph of Fig. 7 shows the different temperature course simulated for the Mühlenfließbrücke at the deck plate following the asphaltting with different asphalt laying temperature, while the other parameters remain constant.

With regard to meteorological climate dependent boundary conditions the initial temperature of the structure obviously has a direct impact on the maximum temperatures within the steel structural elements following the hot asphaltting. While a constant variation of the initial temperature as well as a change of radiation emission leads to a basically constant temperature change over the whole cross section, the gradient variation of the initial temperature (as being caused by direct solar irradiation or diurnal variation) has clearly more impact on the temperatures of the deck plate and decreasing impact with distance from the deck plate. Here also as an example, the bottom graph of Fig. 7 shows the different temperature course simulated for the Mühlenfließbrücke at the deck plate following the asphaltting with different initial temperatures.

Just those two exemplary results in Fig. 7 clearly indicate already the significant difference of the temperatures at the deck plate. With that full parametric study on the local FEM model it is possible to demonstrate the potential to influence the temperatures within the steel structure following the laying of hot mastic asphalt by selecting and combining appropriate parameters. To this end a worst-case- and best-case-scenario examination has been carried out for different deck plate thicknesses: The potential temperature range at the deck plate varies between 79 °C to 129 °C (for a deck plate thickness of $t=10$ mm), between 75 °C to 123 °C (for a deck plate thickness of $t=12$ mm) and between 70 °C to 118 °C (for a deck plate thickness of $t=14$ mm).

Fig. 7. Transient temperature evolution at the deck plate for the Mühlenfließbrücke – parametric variation of asphalt laying temperature (above) and of the initial temperature, gradient over the CS (below)

4.2 Combined stress analysis simulated with FEM and lamella model

When evaluating the results from the application of the combined analysis method using the lamella model to obtain longitudinal stresses over the cross section as well as longitudinal displacements at the start and end abutment, it needs to be pointed out, that any determination of static mechanic values is decisively influenced by the static system of the bridge and geometry of the specific structure. Also, for the “Mühlenfließbrücke” under consideration, only the asphaltting between the two main girders of the open bridge section is evaluated.

However, also with regard to both the stresses over the bridge cross section as well as the deformations along the bridge it can be seen clearly for the investigated bridge model, that like for the temperature fields on the section model, a specific variation and combination of parameters of the hot asphaltting has a significant potential to affect those stresses and deformations following the laying of hot asphalt. This means also, in particular a potentially favourably selection is possible, of course with regard to process dependent parameters, but also those meteorological climate dependent boundary conditions should be observed, even though they are not explicitly adjustable by choice.

All three investigated asphaltting process dependent parameters (variation of asphalt laying temperature, laying speed and width of the paving track) show a significant influence. As could be expected, the variation of the asphalt laying temperature shows a direct linear correlation. Other than has been observed for the thermal parametric study on the local FEM model the variation of the laying speed as well as of the width of the paving track also cause significant changes of the calculated stresses and deformations: A reduction of the paving track width leads to an increase of compression stresses within the deck plate, but at the same time among all calculated variations to the most significant reduction of tension stresses at the sidelong lever arms. On the other hand, the most significant increase of displacements at the end abutment has been calculated for a variation of the maximum laying speed (2.5 m/min).

Investigating the meteorological climate dependent boundary conditions shows that the compression stresses are less when the initial temperature of the bridge structure is higher. For the case, that the deck plate of the bridge structure has already a higher temperature than the rest of the cross section below (i.e. from direct solar irradiation, causing a temperature gradient), the temperature induced tension stresses from asphalt laying are relatively lower. With regard to the abutment displacements it should be noted that any deformation from the hot asphalt laying adds onto other deformations from other temperature increases (for example in the summer).

The following Fig. 8 shows again exemplarily some results with regard to those stresses in the deck plate as well as the abutment displacements under variation of the asphalt laying temperature. Just by only looking at these parameter variations it can be seen, that both stresses or end displacements may be changed by approximately 40%.

Fig. 8. Longitudinal stress development over time at the deck plate next to the main girder (above left) and at the short cantilever (below left), positions as indicated (above right) and displacement over time at start and end abutment – parametric variation of asphalt laying temperature for the Mühlenfließbrücke

5 CONCLUSION AND PROSPECT

The results derived from the analysis with the local FEM model confirm findings from previous investigations with regard to the effect of different parameters. Beyond that, the precise selection of those investigated parameters and their boundaries lead to a far more specific and quantitative evaluation of the influences of those parameters as could be demonstrated exemplarily above.

Clearly, the investigations with the combined stress analysis also confirm cause-and-effect correlations being described from experiences subsequently following hot asphalt laying, like the increase of tension induced cracks and bearing displacement defects. In particular the use of the simplified lamella model allows to evaluate these effects also with distance to the actual temperature input, which so far were not possible to be assessed precisely. Using the new calculation method of the combined analysis with the developed lamella model allows for a first time to quantify the

described effects depending on the different investigated parameter variations, here exemplarily carried out for the selected bridge of the “Mühlenfließbrücke”.

At this time, the newly developed lamella model considers only displacements within the lamella plane and rotations perpendicular to the lamella plane. This means that for example so far, an evaluation of displacements in the cross direction, for example at the bearings, is not possible. To also investigate those displacements, there is the option to further develop the lamella model to include additional necessary degrees of freedom.

Also, it should be noted that at this point so far, a transfer of this method towards investigating the impact of hot asphaltting for other bridge structures, not only other steel bridges but also including composite bridges remains open.

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